

THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA AS A STRATEGIC APPROACH TO CORPORATE COMMUNICATION WHEN HANDLING CRISES AT A SELECTED SOUTH AFRICAN BANK

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of social media as a strategic approach to corporate communication when handling crises at Bank X in the Gauteng province of South Africa. The study had three over-arching objectives; to determine the challenges that are encountered when handling crises about communication at Bank X, to determine if the leadership has the willingness to change their approach when formulating the strategy; to determine if social media has an impact on strategy formulation of crisis communication at Bank X; and lastly to make recommendations to Bank X's leadership on how to incorporate the social media component as a communication approach to effectively handle crises. This research followed a qualitative research approach through one-on-one Microsoft Teams in-depth interviews with 10 participants. The study, through the analysis of the primary data, secondary data, and literature reviews, underpins and supports that there is an opportunity for Bank X to incorporate social media as a strategic element to the crisis communication strategy. The organisation's crisis communication strategy needs to incorporate social media from a strategic perspective for it to be ahead of the curve when a crisis emerges online. The implications for Bank X are a lesson in the evolution of technology in the communication space and how imperative it is for the bank to evolve.

Keywords: social media, crises, communication, impact, Bank, corporate communication, strategic approach, leadership, Gauteng province South Africa.

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1. Introduction

Social media platforms may be defined as Internet-based, computer-mediated communication applications with features that enable users to build up a personal profile and a group of connections, and to create, share and exchange user-generated content in real-time as defined by [1]. There is a large amount of relevant literature on social media in crisis communication, this research focused on how the banking industry specifically incorporates this into their crisis communication strategy or if they used it as a tactical element of the execution plan. A crisis is defined as a significant threat to operations that can have negative consequences if not handled properly. In crisis management, the threat is the potential damage a crisis can inflict on an organization, its stakeholders, and an industry [2].

It has been established, that Bank X does not consider social media as an integral part of their crisis strategy and this approach needed to be investigated to determine what the implication of not incorporating this channel from the onset of the strategy formulation meant.

Social media plays a crucial role in connecting people and developing relationships, not only with key influencers and journalists, covering a specific company's sector, but also provides a great opportunity to establish customer service by gathering input, answering questions, and listening to their feedback states [3]. There are various social media platforms, namely, Facebook, WhatsApp, TikTok, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, and Instagram for example, this study focused on two specific channels (Twitter and LinkedIn), which are communication channels that Bank X uses. Twitter is an American microblogging and social networking service, on which users post and interact with messages, known as "tweets". Registered users can post, like, and retweet tweets, but unregistered users can only read those that are publicly available [3]. Social networks are of significant analytical interest because their data is generated in great quantity, and intermittently, besides that, the data is from a wide variety, and it is widely available to users. Through such data, it is desired to extract knowledge or information that can be used in decision-making activities. It has been established, that Bank X does not consider social media as an integral part of their crisis strategy formulation and this approach needed to be investigated to determine what the implication of not incorporating it from the onset is.

Currently, in the communication department of Bank X, social media is not part of the planning when dealing with crisis communication. When a crisis communication strategic approach is discussed social media is not part of the initial planning phase, it almost comes as an after-thought. This means that there is a glaring gap in the overall communication that goes out to stakeholders during a crisis, resulting in a reactive approach instead of a proactive approach. In this study the researcher wanted to understand if there are any risks, associated with this approach, and if so, make recommendations to Bank X on how to close that gap. In a corporate communication context, a crisis can generate a lot of discussion on social media, and organizations need to be proactive by using strategies to reinforce organizational reputation [4]. Such strategies can for example concern engaging stakeholders through social media in helping the organizations find best solutions for responding to the crisis.

The aim of the study is to investigate the impact of social media as a strategic approach in corporate communication when handling crises: Case of Bank X, Gauteng province. This research attempts to assist the senior managers in the communication department of Bank X to formulate strategies that will consider the various communication channels, which our audience consume news of Bank X from.

This research examined previous studies and identifies research gaps. The biggest gap, found here, is that there is little or no inclusion of social media in the initial strategic planning and conceptualising phase, which could lead to crucial steps, being missed when the tactical process gets executed. The research looked at how the leadership team formulates their strategy and what their success was in terms of implementation, the researcher also looked at various literature reviews on similar studies. The aim of this research was to find out if the current process is as efficient as can be and if there can be room for improvement that could also identify best practices to help the communication team to use social media effectively as a communication channel. The theory was explored thoroughly, and the findings of the study highlighted what Bank X in the financial services industry take into consideration when they formulate the strategy for crisis communication. The purpose was to guide Bank X to consider a different approach when formulating the strategy for crisis communication. This study focused on Bank X specifically, however the researchers hoped that other financial institutions will draw from the findings and apply it to their own institutions. This study also added new knowledge and literature on strategically planning crisis communication, incorporating social media.

While there have been many studies, done previously on social media usage during a crisis, there has not been a specific focus on how organizations use it as part of the strategy

instead of using it as a tactical element. The topic is Investigating the impact of social media as a strategic approach in corporate communication when handling crises: Case of Bank X, Gauteng province. The theory is explored thoroughly, and the findings of the study highlighted what Bank X in the financial services industry needed to take into consideration when they formulate the strategy for crisis communication.

Social media can be defined as internet-based communication platforms, which enable users to create a personal platform to connect and engage with other connections on the platform. Users create original content and share user-generated content in real time [5]. Social media is part of our daily routines and it seamlessly integrates with traditional media and our societal structures. Crisis managers and communicators need to understand the massive potential that both social and traditional media channels have, because people interact and engage on those mediums daily. It is part of everyone's daily lives [2].

Organizational crisis is as an event, perceived by managers and stakeholders as highly salient, unexpected, and potentially disruptive, which can threaten the reputation of the organization [6]. From our literature review, we recognize that the internal perspective focuses on crisis leadership, while the external perspective focuses on stakeholder perceptions of the crisis. In crisis communication, stakeholders prefer social media as opposed to issuing a press release via traditional media [7]. It can be argued, that both channels are necessary during a crisis, one cannot eliminate the other, but instead ensure that in the strategy formulation they are both considered. Social media use is increasing, and new types of uses are being explored, it would make sense that the way a crisis is communicated does not fall far behind [8]. The numbers in **Fig. 1** show how this communication channel has grown and provide empirical evidence that it cannot be ignored as a channel [9].

Fig. 1. Social Media use by Age group : G1 (n=647), G2 (n=234), G3 (N=124)

Facebook and Twitter have grown in South Africa at around 100,000 new users a month in 2015. Based on the growth rate in South Africa alone and among the youth we can deduce that these channels are growing at a rapid pace and changing the way people consume information. To stay abreast of these changes, the organisation needs to ensure that they communicate to their audience on their preferred channel.

2. Materials and Methods

In this study, an interpretivist research philosophy has been selected, using an inductive approach, the subjective views, experiences, and thoughts of the participants will be analyzed and interpreted. An interpretivist philosophy can be studied in detail, especially in multifaceted social processes and in areas where there is insufficient prior theory [10].

In this study, the researcher went the qualitative route because the insights required are of an in-depth nature. The researchers were required to extract opinions, to derive rich explanations, views and suggestions from the respondents and the best way that was obtained was through conversation.

Exploratory qualitative research design was chosen for the study; this ensured that the researchers addressed the research problem adequately. It was important to obtain the depth of how the respondents viewed the impact of social media as a strategic approach in corporate communication when handling crises. Exploratory research design allowed for further probing, which provided the respondents an opportunity to get deeper insights into the problem.

The research strategy, which was selected for this study, was in-depth interviews because the aim of this study was to extrapolate the information directly from the decision makers in the organisation and in doing interviews the researcher was able to gain a better understanding of the participants in-depth thought through responses.

In this study the researcher used purposive sampling for this research. In this study 10 participants from the communication leadership team, residing in Johannesburg, Gauteng, were interviewed, they were chosen from a community of 100 communication specialists in Bank X. These participants were chosen because they have a direct influence in the overall crisis communication strategy formulation.

In this study, participation is voluntary; hence no respondent will be forced to participate. In essence, no one is forced in any way to respond to the questionnaire unwillingly. Participants were notified that they can pull out at any time.

For this study, a face-to-face interview using MS Teams (due to Covid-19 restriction) was used to collect data. One-to-one interviews are used to explore views, opinions, and beliefs of individual participants, whereas focus groups are used to collate qualitative data amongst a group of participants [11]. The researcher made use of individual interviews to gain insights and understand the impact that social media has on the crisis communication strategy. Data was analysed using the thematic analysis method.

3. Presentation of findings

The demographics of the 10 respondents who participated in the interviews consisted of the following subcategories (Table 1).

Table 1
Demographics of the respondents

Respondents	Gender	Age	Race	Qualification	Position	Years of service
Respondent 1	Female	34	African	Post Graduate Diploma	Digital content consultant	4
Respondent 2	Female	43	Indian	Bachelor's Degree	General manager – Communications	6
Respondent 3	Female	35	African	Master's Degree	Communication Specialist	8
Respondent 4	Male	46	Coloured	Bachelor's Degree	Communication Specialist	10
Respondent 5	Female	35	African	Bachelor's Degree	Communication Specialist	8
Respondent 6	Female	46	African	Bachelor's Degree	Media Relations	5
Respondent 7	Female	52	Coloured	Post Graduate Diploma	Communication Specialist	3
Respondent 8	Male	51	African	PHD – Doctorate	Communication Specialist	7
Respondent 9	Female	46	White	Master's Degree	Communication Specialist	9
Respondent 10	Male	52	African	Bachelor's Degree	Head of Communication	4
	Average	44				6.4

Age and Gender of respondents

Fig. 2 indicates that the age of the respondents (male and female) who were interviewed was 35 and above, specifically, one can observe that in the category 35–45 there were 3 participants

however in the category 46–56 there were 6 participants with only one participant in the category 25–35. The observation could be made that the average age in this sample is 44 years of age and those are the key communication people in Bank X. It can also be deduced from the graph, that out of the ten respondents who participated in the study, 7 of them are female and 3 were male. Based on the study conducted it can be assumed, that there are more females in the communication department in Bank X. It is interesting to observe, that there are more female leaders who are at the table, making key decisions in this area of the business.

Fig. 2. Respondents Age and Gender

Level of Qualifications of Respondents

The level of education among the 10 respondents is as follows (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Respondents Qualification Levels

Based on the information, provided by our respondents, is that the highest qualification in the sample size is a PHD in communications, followed by master’s degrees, and all the respondents have a communication qualification, which indicates that they are knowledgeable on the subject that they are being interviewed about.

Years of service of respondents

The average number of years of service of the respondents is 6.4 years. The combined number of years speaks to the level of collective knowledge and experience the team has; it also clearly indicates the loyalty in Bank X. The longest years of service amongst this group is 10 years and the least number of years is 3 years (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Years of service

To determine if social media has an impact in the strategy formulation of crisis communication at Bank X

The aim was to gain a better understanding of the impact that social media has on the overall crisis communication strategy, this was important to investigate whether it should be considered in the strategy and if it the impact of incorporating it is negative or positive.

The question was responded to by all the respondents with a direct yes, they believed that it does have an important role to play in the strategy because we cannot ignore such an important channel during a crisis, it simply cannot be ignored.

Respondent 4 had the following to say: *“I think it’s absolutely critical in formulating that strategy for crisis communication. Over the last decades we’ve moved away from using traditional media platforms and migrated onto social media almost completely”*

Respondent 5 stated that: – *“Very much so, I think I think it is a very important medium for communication. Because unlike the other mediums that we have within the communication space. It is one of the ones that have the most immediate impact and the most immediate feedback from the target audience, which is the public or the consumer on the ground but very few of those mediums allow us to have an immediate point of feedback.”*

Respondent 6 point of view:” – *I think social media has a place. In the way that we communicate, and we consume information has evolved. And if you think about the fact that from a demographic perspective the people that are consuming social media that youngest people in South Africa is a young society, so then you can assume that if we want to reach South Africa, there’s no way of doing that without having a very clear plan about how we’re going to do it on social media. So, it has a place. And when you think about the evolution that we have seen in the past decade, that’s how people would get information via journalists via the story in the newspaper”*

Finding 1

The respondents had a unanimous view that there is definitely an impact that social media has on the formulation of the crisis communication strategy, respondents expressed their views on how the channel cannot be ignored because we live in the fourth industrial revolution, majority of the news our target audience consume is on social media and that it is an expectation for the audience to be able to consume the news on the channel due to convenience and the speed, at which information travels. The traditional way of receiving news has changed and now the news first break on social media and then get published in traditional media, where in the past that was the other way around.

As stated in the Literature review, social media has become significant since it is the primary domain, in which many people receive vast amounts of information, share content and aspects of their lives with others, and receive information about the world around them [12]. Social media allows businesses to communicate directly with all their stakeholders, it is easy to track the conversation and do reporting of the crisis. Social media offers opportunities as well as challenges at the

rapid speed it is developing. The platform is a huge crisis communication platform that cannot be ignored, especially between modern organisations and stakeholders [13].

To determine the challenges, which are encountered when handling crises in relation to communication at Bank X.

This question was asked to determine the respondent's perspective on the challenges, encountered when handling a communication crisis, it is important to understand and explore the respondent's view on the possible hindrance.

The respondents had various views when it came to the different challenges encountered, the main theme, emerging from their responses, was that the approach internally was very reactive as opposed to proactively handling a crisis. Some of the views that were expressed as a concern are the decentralized model versus the centralized operating model that when the business is operating in does bring its own challenges in the organisation.

Respondent 1 – *"We are generally reactive"*

Respondent 2 – *"I think that we use it reactively. We don't use social media, which is a platform for two-way engagement, we don't use it to engage our audience."*

Respondent 5 – *"centralizing that function allows that we don't have, you know duplications or differential messaging that's out there. It also makes it easier for stakeholders. Awareness and oversight of everything that's happening, so that they're able to implement those changes and use that decision making power. But it's hard to do that when pockets of information or sitting in different areas of the business they haven't been fully shared, and so it's very difficult to adjust in the process of managing a crisis."*

Respondent 6 – *"I think for the most part we do it reactively. When it comes, specifically when we're talking about crisis, we do. We do it reactively because we are a very conservative organization in the way we tend to come to communicate with our stakeholders"*

Respondent 8 – *"You know, in trying to formulate the responses to that particular crisis that's happening, that's playing out on social media. A trying to get information you know from business itself, and you know that would take quite a long time. You know, for business to revert with relevant answers, whereas if everything is centralized, the nice thing about that is that at least you are sending out one message you want, so if you add decentralized and you are not aligned and there's no proper coordination of you know of what each area is doing and how they're responding to that issue or that issue you end up giving out you know sort of schizophrenic"*

Respondent 11 – *"I typically observe it as a customer that we are very reactive, so the paw-paw hits the fan and then we will go out. It's very seldom that we would be proactive and issue."*

Finding 2

80 % of the respondents indicated that a primary challenge is that social media is used reactively in crisis communication and not approached from a proactive perspective, they also indicated that the decentralized operating model is proving challenging when dealing with a crisis due to complications in the approval process and the way one gets perceived by the audience. As stated by Dong (2017), crisis management on social media is particularly challenging because crises, emerging online, are rather unpredictable and can upgrade quickly. Due to social media being so unpredictable, it is important to plan diligently and have a proactive plan in place, which puts the organisation in a better position to handle the crisis. Audiences seek out social media during crises, because it provides an unfiltered, up-to-date line of communication, and provide unique crisis information that audiences cannot get elsewhere [14]. Search for information related to crises through social media on a mobile platform, is high during a crisis, due to the speed, convenience, ease of access, compared to traditional media.

To determine if the leadership team have the appetite to change their approach when formulating the strategy

This question was posed to the respondents to understand what their view was about the leadership team's perceptions about social media, and this was important to understand because some of these respondents were the key leaders, sitting at the table, making these decisions. So, understanding how they think when making key decisions and what their concerns were with the platform was imperative to the researcher.

Respondent 3 – *“I don’t know whether it’s a lack of appetite or interest, or simply just lack of understanding of what this?”*

Respondent 4 – *“No, they wouldn’t.”*

Respondent 6 – *“You can’t change what you don’t have knowledge of, so for people to address something and have the appetite to do something about it is for there to be an acknowledgement that you know what there a gap is here, and we need to do something about it. We have a situation such as the one that we have is because there is a fundamental misunderstanding of this function, and a fundamental disregard for what the function brings on the table. So how then are they going to be thinking about how do we fix this social media problem? What problem? There’s none. “*

Respondent 7 – *“I’m not sure what the barrier is. I’m not sure if they fearful of saying the wrong or right thing or I feel like they’re not brave enough to encourage open and honest conversation”*

Finding 3

The respondents all indicate that they did not believe that the leadership team has the appetite to change their approach. There seems to be a misunderstanding of the function and what it brings to the table. This is then further exacerbated by the fact that the function is not brought to the table in the beginning of the strategy formulation process, which then further makes it difficult for the function to be proactive. A further point was made around fearfulness and being risk adverse nature of the business, which causes them to shy away from social media. As indicated in the literature review, a good leader is adaptable and flexible, which allows them to navigate change successfully [15]. Based on the feedback from the respondents, it doesn’t seem like the leaders in Bank X are ready to adapt and accept fully that social media is a medium that cannot be ignored any longer and it needs to be considered at the start of any strategy formulation because the way, in which our audience consume information, has changed. While there are various studies on social media across disciplines, there is no conceptual framework for organizing, guiding, and inspiring research on social media engagement among strategic leaders yet, and this is a gap that needs to be closed [16].

To make recommendations to Absa leadership on how to incorporate the social media component as a communication approach to effectively handle crises.

It is fundamental to provide recommendations to the leadership team on how they can overcome certain barriers encountered and provide solutions to current problems, encountered in the business. The best people to provide solutions are the respondents because they understand the problems well enough to come up with suitable solutions.

Respondent 2 – *“To actually get all the role players in the room. So that all players that are involved early, the role players that are involved late to get all that players to map, uh, process so. And we’ve done some of this work and I feel like. I think that we need to actually document our process.”*

Respondent 3 – *“I think much like what I was saying around which strategies formulated have the right individuals at the table.”*

Respondent 4 – *“I think of first the most important part is that the communication team should have a seat at that executive table”*

Respondent 6 – *“So, for me that is where it starts. I think it is quite unacceptable for an organization of this size that we are still talking social media manager. We should be talking social media strategies. We should be talking social media, managing principle.”*

R5 - within the organization, but they’re able to keep a record of pending risks

Finding 4

The respondents indicated that there was room for improvement with the current strategy, 70 % of the respondents indicated that the first recommendation is for the right people to sit at the table when the strategy is formulated. 20 % of the respondents indicated that while it is important to have the right people at the table, we should also map out a blueprint process of how a crisis should be handled, and 10 % of the respondents believed that a record should be kept of pending risks. Effective crisis communication in the enterprise should be planned and successfully managed, since every crisis has its life cycle, which can be influenced. The missing link between formulation of the

strategy crisis communication and its implementation provides a strategic map, which is logical and coherent architecture for description of the crisis communication strategy. A strategy map of crisis communication shows the achievement of corporate objective, which in times of crisis is the stability of the company. The role that social media play in crisis management is crucial; therefore, the importance of where in the strategy process it is considered makes a huge difference in the outcome

This study is not a representation of all the banks in South Africa, it was limited to Bank X. The small size of the sample population could be regarded as a further key limitation to the study even though the researcher tried to ensure that there was an equal representation of the sample population, the possibility still exists that the respondents did not cover an ample sample segmentation, therefore the findings of this study cannot be generalized.

The research is limited to Bank X communication teams' perceptions. Other researchers in the field could focus on various other facets of this topic to add to the work already completed. Research needs to be done on the why older leaders are not open to change and adaptation in technology. Research also needed to be done on the how often would a crisis communication strategy need to be reviewed to stay ahead of the changes in the social media landscape.

4. Conclusions

Findings from this study indicated that social media has positive impact on the crisis communication strategy. The crisis communication strategy in its current form has several shortcomings that can be improved on. It is recommended that:

- The communications team has a digital media strategist at the table when they are formulating the crisis communication strategy to ensure that the social media component is considered right upfront
- Considering social media as part of the strategy and not as a reactive tactic will ensure that the Bank X is steering the conversation in the cycle and not playing catch-up, while the crisis erupts
- Bank X needs to make sure that it keeps a reputation risk register, which has a record of all the risks across the business that could potentially lead to a reputational issue. They also need to ensure that they map out the process when dealing with reputations and have simulation exercises to be able to identify any risks that may unfold
- All the leaders need to go for ongoing training on social media to ensure that they are understand the landscape very well and that they are aware of the benefits and the risks of the platform

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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